

Smartphone addiction: psychosocial correlates, risky attitudes, and smartphone harm

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ABSTRACT

Smartphone use has brought convenience to users, although its excessive use and addiction might also have negative consequences. Using a representative sample of 526 smartphone users in Spain, the present study analyzes smartphone extensive use and addiction as well as its relationship to smartphone harm. Self-reported and scanned data were obtained from users and their smartphones. Multivariate linear regression analyses showed that higher levels of smartphone extensive use were found for female respondents, those high on general propensity to risk, neuroticism, and low on conscientiousness, openness, or social support. Multivariate binary logistic results showed that general propensity to risk and low social support were predictive of smartphone addiction. The combination of high smartphone extensive use and low social support was positively and significantly related to the existence of smartphone harm as well as higher levels of risk attitudes toward smartphone use. These results might indicate that when low social support is coupled with an extensive smartphone use, respondents not only show a more positive attitude toward risky behaviors while using their smartphone but, also, a greater level of harm is found in their terminals.

1. Introduction

The study of the addiction to smartphones has traditionally focused on the explanatory mechanisms of addiction and its consequences for the psychosocial well-being of users. However, addiction to the smartphone also carries potentially harmful consequences for the security of the devices themselves that has negative implications for the safety of users. Despite its harmful consequences, however, the study of the implications of smartphone addiction on the user's safety has been traditionally neglected in the literature. In the present study, we analyze the correlates of extensive use and smartphone addiction in 526 smartphone users drawn from a representative sample of Internet users in Spain. In addition, we also analyze the relationship between extensive use and addiction to smartphone and risk behaviors of users. These risk behaviors are also linked to the vulnerability of the devices and security threats to users.

Smartphone ownership rates in emerging and developing nations are rising at an extraordinary rate, climbing from a median of 21% in 2013 to 37% in 2015% (Poushter 2016). In Spain, where the present study was undertaken, smartphone ownership in the adult population is above 71%, which is

among the highest country rates in the world and the first one in the European Union (Deloitte 2015; Poushter 2016).

The World Health Organization (WHO 2015) has suggested that excessive use of the Internet and electronic devices—including smartphones—typically presents physical health problems (see also Dong, Huang, and Du 2012), injuries and accidents, or infections. Among the psychosocial consequences, WHO (2015) points out to the existence of problems in areas such as violence (i.e. cyber-bullying, aggressive behaviors), social development (i.e. social withdrawal), sleep deprivation, risky sexual behaviors, or other social or psychological problems such as poor psychological well-being, family, or work problems.

1.1. Correlates of smartphone addiction

Personality characteristics and poor social relationships are among the most relevant risk factors to have an effect on smartphone addiction (WHO 2015). Individuals characterized by low agreeableness, high extraversion, low conscientiousness, or high neuroticism have been found to be prone to cell phone and Internet addiction (Andreassen et al. 2013; Bianchi and Phillips 2005; Hardie and Tee 2007; Lepp et al. 2015; Mowen 2000; Müller et al. 2013; Roccas et al. 2002; Stieger et al. 2013; Yao et al. 2014). In their review of 68 large-scale empirical studies on Internet Addiction since the year 2000, Kuss et al. (2014) found that low social support was significantly associated with Internet addiction. According to Billieux et al. (2015) individuals low on social support would make an extensive use of smartphones in order to obtain reassurance in affective and close relationships, being loneliness and low satisfaction with life accompanying psychological correlates (Wang et al. 2015). This would be in line with the dependent user described by Lu et al. (2011), who shows poor adult attachment models and high levels of problematic use of mobile phones. It is also consistent with research finding that people who extensively use their smartphones for social purposes develop smartphone habits faster, which in turn might lead to addictive smartphone behavior (van Deursen et al. 2015).

1.2. Smartphone use, smartphone addiction and smartphone harm

Despite the increasing interest researchers have devoted to the study of psychosocial correlates of smartphone extensive use and addiction, less scholarly attention has been directed to the security consequences of smartphone addiction. In this sense, Pramod and Raman (2014) have suggested that in an era of smartphone addiction the security aspects might become a cause for concern (Urueña and Hidalgo 2016). As Herrero et al. (forthcoming) have pointed out, despite security warnings users still put themselves and their equipment at risk, compromising not only the security of their smartphones but also their personal safety due to potential cyber-victimization. In their study on risk attitudes and perceptions toward computer use, Herrero et al. (forthcoming) found that both general and domain-specific risk-taking were positively related to the existence of users' computers harm. Risk-taking propensity has been used to explain why some individuals are likely to favor risky decisions and engage in risky activities. This general propensity to risk has been claimed to be positively related to both problematic Internet use (Ko et al. 2007; Lin and Tsai 2002; Velezmoro, Lacefield, and Roberti 2010) and problematic use of mobile phones (Billieux, Van der Linden, and Rochat 2008). In this regard, Billieux et al. (2015), described a type of problematic mobile phone user with high levels of sensation-seeking that have an increased probability of carrying out mobile risk behaviors.

1.3. The present study

According to the above, there is empirical evidence about the relationship between users' individual characteristics, their social relationships and the extensive use and addiction to the smartphone. However, less is known about how these characteristics responsible for the extensive use and addiction to the smartphone can in turn favor risky behaviors in smartphones that, in fact, compromise their security. The present study seeks precisely to analyze these influences.

To do so, the present study seeks to combine both the literature on psychosocial correlates of smartphone extensive use and addiction and the literature on risk-taking to answer the following research questions: (a) what are the correlates of smartphone extensive use and addiction? and (b) what is the relationship among smartphone extensive use and addiction, risk attitudes and perceptions of smartphone use and smartphone harm?

To achieve objective goals, we analyze data from 526 smartphone users drawn from a representative sample of Internet users in Spain. Two types of information were used for this study. First, self-reported measures about sociodemographic characteristics, personality, social support, risk attitudes, smartphone extensive use, and addiction were obtained online (self-reported data). Second, users' smartphones were remotely scanned upon approval of respondents with a software to search for resident malware in users' terminals –scanned data – (see Herrero et al., [forthcoming](#) for a similar approach).

Personality was assessed through the Big Five model of personality as it has been reported in the literature its relationship with smartphone extensive use and addiction (Kuss, Griffiths, and Binder 2013; Kuss et al. 2013, 2014). Also, general propensity to risk (i.e. sensation-seeking) was assessed given the available empirical evidence on its relationship to problematic Internet use (Ko et al. 2007), hazardous use of mobile phones (Billieux et al. 2015) and risk behaviors on computers and Internet (Herrero et al., [forthcoming](#)). Related to the analysis of potential risk to smartphones, we included a domain-specific measure of risk attitudes and perceptions of smartphone use. Following research showing that the necessity to maintain close relationships might be related to smartphone addiction (Billieux et al. 2015) we assessed social support of participants. Finally, to better control for potentially biased responses we used a measure of social desirability. This was specially the case for the measurement of smartphone extensive use and addiction that presumably could have presented potentially biased responses among participants.

2. Method

2.1. Participants

We used data from the Cybersecurity and Confidence in Spanish Households national survey conducted between September and December 2015 by the National Observatory of Telecommunications and Information Society of the Spanish Ministry of Industry. The survey was designed to measure cybersecurity in digitalized Spanish households. Two types of data were used in the survey: reported and scanned data. Reported data referred to the responses that participants gave to the online questionnaire. Scanned data were obtained from scanning of smartphones upon approval of participants. The information about the existence of malicious software –malware– in respondent's smartphones was collected through the use of an Android app developed to perform security analysis. This app analyzed the presence of malware through the use of 50 antivirus engines without interfering in the performance of the device. The app was installed in participants' smartphones to regularly search for resident malware and to collect data about the operative system, their up-to-date status and the presence of installed security tools.

Participants belonged to a representative sample of the Spanish population of Internet users 15 years old and over with residential Internet access. Primary sampling units were households and secondary sampling units were individuals within households. First, a Spanish representative sample of households in terms of Autonomous Communities, size of locality, social class, and number of persons in household were selected. Second, Internet users 15 years old and over within households were identified and selected.

For this study, we used data from 526 smartphone users who completed the online questionnaire and, also, whose smartphones were remotely scanned to gather data on malware (viruses, spy software, trojans, worms, etc.) as well as security measures that were active at the time of scanning. Only smartphones running on Android operative system were scanned, since they represent 87.8% of market share in Spain and 84.1% worldwide (Statista 2016a, 2016b). Related to this, the increasing number of

Android-based smartphones has probably led to an exponential rise in Android malware apps (Faruki et al. 2015) which has become a cause for concern for technical, governmental, and legal experts. To additionally control for potentially biased responses, questions were randomly presented.

2.2. Variables and scales

2.2.1. Socio-demographic variables

Socio-demographic variables were: sex (male 51.9%, female 48.1%), age in five age groups years (15–24, 25–34, 35–44, 45–54, 55+, $M = 2.76$, $S.D. = 1.21$), educational background (highest educational level attainment, from 1 –elementary– to 3 –university studies–, $M = 2.38$, $S.D. = 0.58$), and size of locality (from 1 less than 10,000 to 6 more than 500,000 inhabitants, $M = 3.82$, $S.D. = 1.74$).

2.2.2. Smartphone addiction symptoms

The Smartphone Addiction Symptoms Scale (SAPS) is a 19-likert item scale that allows identification of smartphone addiction symptoms and to assess overall level of smartphone addiction (Bian and Leung 2015). Category responses ranged from 1 = completely disagree to 5 = completely agree. Overall, internal consistency for the 19 items was high (Cronbach's $\alpha = .95$). The averaged mean of smartphone addiction symptoms among participants of the study was slightly lower ($M = 2.12$, $S.D. = 0.74$) than that reported by Bian and Leung (2015) in their study on 414 Chinese college students ($M = 2.55$, $S.D. = 0.67$) ($t = 9.21$, $p < .001$).

2.2.3. Extent of smartphone addiction

Following Bian and Leung (2015) approach, we assessed the extent to which users were addicted to smartphones from the 8 items of the SAPS that were most conceptually equivalent to Young's (1996) screening instrument in Internet addiction. Those items were first dichotomized (1 to 3 recoded to '0', and 4 to 5 recoded to '1'). These 8 items were summed, which yielded a value ranging from '0' to '8'. Further, respondents with a score of 5 or above were classified as addicts. According to these criteria, 6.6% in the sample were addicted to smartphones. Bian and Leung (2015) found that 13.5% of their sample were addicted to smartphones. This difference is highly significant as compared to the addicted users found in our study ($\chi^2(3) = 13.14$, $p < .001$). Although the authors recently published the scale, it is being extensively used for research due to its ability to provide the extent of smartphone addiction according to several DSM-IV criteria.

2.2.4. Personality

An abbreviated version of the Big Five Inventory (BFI) (Rammstedt and John 2007) was used to measure personality traits of the Big Five model. This short version of the BFI has been extensively used for researchers and it is specially indicated to obtain a valid and reliable measure of personality traits when the participant's time is limited, as in our case. Also, BFI has been used in studies on the relationship between the big five model of personality and addictions (Pawlikowski, Altstötter-Gleich, and Brand 2013). The abbreviated version of the BFI uses 10 items with category responses ranging from 1 = completely disagree to 5 = completely agree. Each trait is measured with two items: extraversion ($M = 3.12$, $S.D. = 0.94$), agreeableness ($M = 3.33$, $S.D. = 0.75$), conscientiousness ($M = 3.77$, $S.D. = 0.85$), neuroticism ($M = 2.63$, $S.D. = 0.92$), and openness ($M = 3.54$, $S.D. = 0.87$).

2.2.5. General propensity to risk

The Brief Sensation-Seeking Scale (BSSS, Hoyle et al. 2002) is a four-item scale that measures trait sensation-seeking. Items responses ranged from 1 = strongly disagree to 5 = strongly agree ($M = 3.30$, $S.D. = 0.75$) (Cronbach's $\alpha = .82$). This brief measure of sensation-seeking was especially developed to be used in large-scale surveys. BSSS scores correlate as expected with a number of drug-related outcomes, as well as risk and protective factors for problem behaviors (Hoyle et al. 2002).

2.2.6. Social support

The strong-tie support (Lin, Dean, and Ensel 1981) was used to measure social support from intimate and confidant relationships with three items in a four-point scale from 1 = never to 5 = most of the time. It measures to what degree respondents felt their support needs from close companions were fulfilled. Cronbach's was .60 ($M = 3.84$, $S.D. = 0.48$) in line with other research (Herrero and Gracia 2011). The three items of the strong-tie support scale are a recommended measure of social support for large-scale surveys due to its brevity (Gracia et al. 2009).

2.2.7. Domain-specific smartphone use risk attitudes and risk perceptions

Domain-specific scales of risk perceptions and attitudes do not traditionally measure domains such as smartphones. Due to this, an adapted version of the Computer Use Risk Perceptions and Risk Attitudes (Herrero et al., *forthcoming*) to measure smartphone risk attitudes and risk perceptions was used. It measures respondents' risk perceptions and risk attitudes of several activities people might engage when using smartphones (1 = no risky to 7 = extremely risky) and, also, the probability that they would engage in those activities (1 = extremely unlikely to 7 = extremely likely). The five items measured activities such as not updating security passwords regularly, not installing antivirus software, not having the latest smartphone operative system updated, to follow links in anonymous messages, and to ignore security warnings when accessing websites of interest. Internal consistency was adequate for both risk perceptions ($\alpha = 0.77$) and attitudes ($\alpha = 0.78$). Pearson's bivariate correlation between risk perceptions and attitudes was significant and negative ($r = -.41$, $p < .001$).

2.2.8. Social desirability

To better control for potential response bias, the Strahan and Gerbasi (1972) short form of the Marlowe–Crowne social desirability scale (Crowne and Marlowe 1960) was used. This short form has shown adequate psychometrical properties and consists of 10 true–false items of the original 33 items scale (1 = True, 2 = False) and it has been used in studies on addiction (Broadus and Evans 2015). Negative items were reversed so that higher scale scores reflect greater levels of social desirability. Scores on all 10 items were summed up and averaged ($M = 1.56$, $S.D. = 0.18$). Social desirability scores were significantly related to smartphone addiction scores ($r = -.21$, $p < .001$) suggesting that respondents biased their responses downwards when reporting about their smartphone addiction symptoms.

2.2.9. Scanned data. Existence of malware

Smartphones were classified as 0 – not infected ($n = 411$, 78%) – and 1 –infected ($n = 115$, 22%) – according to the presence of detected malware in the smartphone.

3. Results

3.1. Preliminary analyses on the internal structure of SAPS

Prior to analyzing the relationships among the variables of the study, we first analyzed the internal structure of the SAPS. Authors reported that the 19 items of the SAPS clustered into five dimensions: *Disregard of harmful consequences* (5 items), *Preoccupation* (5 items), *Inability to control craving* (4 items), *Productivity Loss* (3 items), and *Feeling anxious and lost* (2 items). In our data, principal components analysis showed that the 19 items clustered into two dimensions, and the Promax rotation solution used indicated that these two dimensions were highly correlated ($r = .79$, $p < .001$). Imposing a five-factor solution did not seem to solve the problem given that the resulting factors were not theoretically meaningful. Confirmatory factor analyses using EQS software (Bentler 2006), showed that a modified five-factor model with two additional correlations among disturbance terms would provide adequate fit to the data: $\chi^2(140) = 461.85$, $CFI = .95$, $RMSEA = 0.64$, 95% confidence interval (0.06, 0.07). This solution, however, estimated a very high correlation among latent factors (ranging from $r = .74$ to $.98$, averaged $r = .88$, all p 's $< .001$) suggesting that a second-order general factor could be explaining the covariation among

Table 1. Smartphone addiction symptoms: results from multivariate linear regression: regression estimates, and probability associated among smartphone users in Spain ($N = 526$).

Variable	Smartphone addiction symptoms ^a		
	β	t	p
<i>Sociodemographic characteristics</i>			
Female	.13	3.08	.002
Age	-.03	-0.82	.935
Educational background	.07	1.88	.061
Size of locality	-.07	-1.74	.062
<i>Personality</i>			
Extraversion	.06	1.42	.156
Agreeableness	.03	0.77	.442
Conscientiousness	-.16	-3.87	.000
Neuroticism	.13	3.17	.002
Openness	-.12	-2.88	.004
<i>Risk and social variables</i>			
General propensity to risk	.25	6.28	.000
Social support	-.20	-5.00	.000
Social desirability	-.09	-2.16	.031

^a $R^2 = .25$, adjusted $R^2 = .23$.

Table 2. Smartphone addiction: results from multivariate logistic binary regression: regression estimates, and probability associated, odds ratios and associated 95% confidence intervals among smartphone users in Spain ($N = 526$).

Variable	Smartphone addiction ^a				
	B	p	Exp(B) Estimate	95% confidence interval	
<i>Sociodemographic characteristics</i>					
Female	0.60	.090	1.83	0.91	3.67
Age	0.29	.874	1.03	0.72	1.48
Educational background	-0.32	.310	1.05	0.73	1.51
Size of locality	0.03	.790	1.03	0.84	1.25
<i>Personality</i>					
Extraversion	0.45	.811	1.05	0.72	1.51
Agreeableness	0.20	.450	1.22	0.73	2.03
Conscientiousness	-0.33	.118	0.72	0.48	1.09
Neuroticism	0.33	.095	1.39	0.94	2.06
Openness	-0.41	.052	0.67	0.44	1.04
<i>Risk and social variables</i>					
General propensity to risk	1.30	.000	3.67	2.25	5.98
Social support	-0.73	.000	0.48	0.33	0.70
Social desirability	-1.60	.087	0.20	0.03	1.26

^aNagelkerke $R^2 = .29$.

first-order factors. We re-estimated the model with a second-order factor explaining all the covariation among first-order factors. This model showed an adequate fit to the data: $\chi^2(145) = 398.53$, CFI = .94, RMSEA = 0.06, 95% confidence interval (0.05, 0.06). In this model, all the standardized second-order loadings were greater than .88 (p 's < .001), suggesting that the factorial structure of the SPAS could be correctly described in our sample with a single and global measure of smartphone addiction symptoms. The general measure of smartphone addiction symptoms was therefore retained for further analyses.

3.2. Covariates of smartphone addiction symptoms and smartphone addiction

For the analysis of covariates, we used multivariate linear regression (for smartphone addiction symptoms), and multivariate logistic binary regression (for smartphone addiction). Model R^2 was also calculated to estimate the global contribution of the model to the prediction of outcome variable. Results are presented in Tables 1 and 2.

Table 3. Results of bi-step cluster analyses: Groups of smartphone users by levels of smartphone addiction symptoms and social support ($N = 526$).

Group	n	Smartphone addiction symptoms	Social support	% of infected smartphones	Risk perceptions	Risk attitudes
Low social support						
High addiction symptoms	90	3.16	2.54	31.81	5.00	3.93
Low addiction symptoms	150	1.75	2.57	24.00	5.24	3.07
High social support						
Low addiction symptoms	186	1.62	4.26	19.89	5.34	2.69
High addiction symptoms	100	2.97	3.92	22.22	5.22	2.98

As for the covariates of smartphone addiction symptoms, results of Table 1 indicate that among the socio-demographic variables only being female was positively related with smartphone addiction symptoms ($\beta = .13, p = .002$). The personality trait of the Big Five neuroticism ($\beta = .13, p = .002$) and the general propensity to risk ($\beta = .25, p < .001$) were positively related to smartphone addiction symptoms. Other Big Five model traits such as conscientiousness ($\beta = -.16, p < .001$) and openness ($\beta = -.12, p = .004$) were negatively related to smartphone addiction symptoms.

Finally, social support was negatively related to smartphone addiction symptoms ($\beta = -.20, p < .001$). These results statistically controlled for the fact that smartphone addiction symptoms measure was significantly affected by social desirability ($\beta = -.09, p = .031$).

Table 2 present the multivariate binary logistic results for the covariates of smartphone addiction. The results show that the only significant covariates of smartphone addiction were being generally prone to risk ($\text{Exp}(B) = 3.67, p < .001$) and having lower levels of social support ($\text{Exp}(B) = 0.48, p = .000$). Also, we found a negative marginal effect for openness ($\text{Exp}(B) = 0.67, p = .052$) and social desirability ($\text{Exp}(B) = 0.20, p = .087$) with smartphone addiction.

3.3. Smartphone addiction symptoms, social support, and risky smartphone use

We further explored if smartphone addiction and social support were predictive of smartphone harm using both self-reported and scanned data. First, we clustered smartphone users according to their levels of smartphone addiction symptoms and social support. Second, we analyzed the extent of smartphone harm of these users through the study of the malware found in their terminals. Finally, we tested if these groups of smartphone users had different risk attitudes and perceptions toward smartphone risky.

Bi-step cluster analysis was first use to find the optimal number of groups of users that best described the distribution of the scores of smartphone addiction symptoms and social support in the sample. Four groups were identified according to their low/high levels in smartphone addiction symptoms and social support (see Table 3).

As for the risk attitudes and perceptions of the four groups of smartphone users, we found that high addiction symptoms/low social support users scored significantly higher on risk attitudes of smartphone use ($M = 3.93, S.D. = 1.38$) –group 1– than the other users: group 2 (low addiction symptoms/low social support; $M = 3.07; S.D. = 1.26$), group 3 (low addiction symptoms/high social support; $M = 2.69, S.D. = 0.97$), and group 4 (high addiction symptoms/high social support $M = 2.98, S.D. = 1.20$) ($F(3, 522) = 23.77, p < .001$). No significant differences were found for risk perceptions ($F(3, 522) = 2.32, ns$).

χ^2 analysis revealed that there were more infected smartphones in group 1 than expected by chance (z value = 2.0, $p < .05$): the highest frequency of infected smartphones was found for users scoring high in smartphone addiction symptoms and low on social support. For users with high smartphone addiction symptoms and high social support, we did not find any statistical relationships with the existence of

an infected smartphone (z value = 0.3, ns). The other two combinations of low smartphone addiction symptoms and social support (low/low and low/high) did not show any statistical relationship with the presence of an infected smartphone (z values of 0.2 and -1.5 , ns, respectively). These findings suggested that under high levels of smartphone addiction symptoms, higher levels of social support were negatively related to the presence of malware in smartphone.

4. Discussion, strengths, and limitations

4.1. Discussion

Literature on the use of the Internet and electronic devices has traditionally warned about their potentially deleterious consequences in users' health (WHO 2015). While most of this research has been focused on Internet and computers (Beard 2002; Beard and Wolf 2001; Chak and Leung 2004; Leung 2004; Young 1998), the propagation of smartphones in society warrants new research efforts to further analyze smartphone extensive use and addiction. Most of the research in this area have been devoted to the effects of smartphone addiction on users' health (see Kuss et al. 2014 for a review of studies) with less scholarly attention directed toward other deleterious consequences such as smartphone harm via potentially risky behaviors. In the present study, we combined these two perspectives of analysis through the study of the correlates of smartphone extensive use and addiction and its relationship to smartphone harm in a representative sample of 526 smartphone users in Spain. For the analysis of smartphone extensive use and addiction, self-reported information on sociodemographic, personality and social support of participants were measured. For the analysis of smartphone harm, information provided by remotely installed software was obtained from each user's smartphone and combined with other self-reported information such as risk attitudes and perceptions on smartphone use.

The first part of the present study sought to analyze psychosocial correlates of smartphone extensive use and addiction. Our results seem to provide empirical evidence to other research showing that both personality and social relationships are important correlates of smartphone extensive use and addiction. Regarding smartphone extensive use, findings suggest that respondents biased downward their self-reported smartphone overuse. After adjusting for response bias, results showed that being female was the only socio-demographic correlate of smartphone extensive use. As for personality, those respondents lower on conscientiousness and openness, higher on neuroticism, or higher on general propensity to risk, scored significantly higher on smartphone extensive use. As for social relationships, lower levels of social support were significantly related to smartphone extensive use. While these socio-demographic, personality, and interpersonal correlates were predictive of higher smartphone extensive use, only high general propensity to risk and low social support were significantly related to smartphone addiction.

Literature has suggested that addictions stem from regular habit-formation processes over time and that some users might develop smartphone extensive use into addictions (Oulasvirta et al. 2012). In this vein, our results suggest that while some of the Big Five personality traits were related to extensive use of smartphone (specifically conscientiousness, openness, and neuroticism) they were not significantly related to addiction, beyond respondents' levels of general propensity to risk and social support. Thus, both sensation-seeking and social support emerged from our data as key predictors of smartphone addiction. The influence of low social support on smartphone addiction gives support to Kuss et al. (2014) claim that smartphone addiction does not occur in a vacuum but it is exacerbated when using smartphones to deal with existing problems. In our study, social support seemed to fit well into this explanation: low social support might have led smartphone users to exacerbate their addiction, while general propensity to risk also influenced smartphone addiction.

In the second part of the study, social support and smartphone extensive use were analyzed with regard to potentially smartphone risk attitudes and perceptions and smartphone harm. As for the level of smartphone harm of these users, results showed that among users with low social support, those with higher smartphone use had a greater chance of having malware in their smartphones, as compared to those with a less extensive smartphone use. Among users with high support, levels of smartphone use

were statistically unrelated to the presence of malware in their smartphones. Also, this low support/high smartphone use respondent showed a greater level of smartphone risk attitudes than the other types of respondents. Taken together these results might indicate that when low social support is coupled with an extensive smartphone use, respondents not only show a more positive attitude toward risky behaviors while using their smartphone but, also, a greater level of harm is found in their terminals. While other authors have also found that low social support might be related to smartphone extensive use and addiction (Billieux et al. 2015) what our study suggests is that a combination of both low social support and high smartphone use potentially leads to smartphone harm. Moreover, this smartphone harm might probably continue to occur over time given the risky attitudes toward smartphone use associated (Herrero et al., [forthcoming](#)).

4.2. Strengths and limitations

Our study presents strengths and potential limitations. Both the national representative sample and the type of information used (self-reported and scanned data) might be regarded as strengths of the study, which probably adds generalizability to study findings (see Herrero et al., [forthcoming](#) for a similar approach). Also, the statistical control of potentially response bias through the analysis of social desirability allowed for a more accurate identification of true effects for the covariates of smartphone extensive use and addiction.

Given the cross-sectional nature of the study, however, directionality of relationships cannot be claimed with our data and other alternative explanations are also tenable. The lack of social interaction and the low perception of social support could be more a consequence than an antecedent of the addiction to the smartphone. In this sense, addicted people could dedicate to the smartphone an excessive time that would lead to greater social isolation, feelings of loneliness, and perception of low social support (WHO 2015). Thus, smartphone extensive use and addiction might have had consequences on the social support of participants, rather than the opposite as we suggested from our data. Our hypothesis that low social support is an antecedent of smartphone extensive use and addiction, however, is consistent with empirical evidence showing that difficulties in social relationships (such as the low levels of support from intimate and confidant social relationships or loneliness) might trigger smartphone addiction (Bian and Leung 2015; Billieux et al. 2015; van Deursen et al. 2015; Kwon et al. 2016). As it has been pointed out in the literature (WHO 2015), the lack of longitudinal studies in this area has traditionally limited the study of causal mechanisms of smartphone extensive use and addiction thus warranting new research efforts that takes into account the temporal dimension (i.e. longitudinal research). In this sense, longitudinal research has suggested that psychologically distressed individuals (i.e. low on self-esteem) might use technology as an escape from their feelings of self and social inadequacy (Witt, Massman, and Jackson 2011). Moreover, smartphone addiction might be the result of trying to cope with these feelings (Billieux et al. 2015; Caplan 2006) as our data seem also to suggest. Despite the appealing of this line of argumentation, new follow-up studies would provide additional insights on the tenability of this hypothesis.

5. Conclusions

Smartphone ownership and use has steadily grown in the last years among the general population. While smartphones have brought convenience to users due to the great deal of functions and apps with available Internet, researchers have recently linked smartphone extensive use and addiction with negative physical, psychological and social outcomes for users (WHO 2015). Moreover, smartphone extensive use and addiction have been claimed to be the result of coping mechanisms where individuals use their smartphones in order to deal with preexisting conditions such as personality characteristics or poor social relationships (Kuss et al. 2014). Our study has empirically found that general propensity to risk and low social support are key to understand smartphone addiction.

Smartphone extensive use and addiction not only have implications for users' psychosocial adjustment (Billieux et al. 2015; Lu et al. 2011; Wang et al. 2015) but it also affects the type of smartphone use. In our study, we found that smartphones belonging to respondents with an extensive smartphone use and low on social support presented the higher rates of vulnerabilities (i.e. malware) and risky attitudes toward smartphone use. This circumstance not only might have implications for the security of the devices but also to users' personal safety (i.e. cyber-victimization).

Our study is one of the first to link the personal and social characteristics of users, their potential addiction to smartphones and the existence of probable risky behaviors with the smartphones. In this sense, this study links the psychological and psychosocial aspects of smartphone use and the vulnerability of smartphones, with the potential negative consequences that could have for user victimization (cybercrime, for example). The main contribution of the present research consists in its attempt to unite two often separate research traditions. What we could call the psychosocial model, analyzes the aspects of well-being related to the extensive use and addiction to the smartphone (Billieux et al. 2015; Lu et al. 2011; van Deursen et al. 2015; WHO 2015). This psychosocial model is also linked to a risk model (Billieux, Van der Linden, and Rochat 2008; Herrero et al., *forthcoming*), where smartphone behaviors and risk perceptions explain the vulnerability and security problems of smartphones (for example, the existence of malware).

The idea that the users' psychosocial needs can lead them to be put at risk due to the type of use they make of their smartphones, opens new avenues for studying risk behaviors and the vulnerability of smartphones. The study of the conditions under which users will compromise their safety and the consequences that for their well-being may have, require new research that incorporates the time dimension (follow-ups). This would allow a clear distinction between antecedents and consequences of smartphone addiction as well as the multiple influences that occur over time between security conditions and psychosocial needs.

Disclosure statement

No potential conflict of interest was reported by the authors.

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